

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** STEPHANE**FIRST NAME:** BONAMY**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** DR. GULMA**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing an academic essay: from researching the topic to structuring the response (EUCLID 2021, 7-12)
2. Choosing a variant: American versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
4. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. How and when to use Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 59-64)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I wrote my last academic essay thirty years ago. It was written in French as part of my dissertation in Contemporary History at the University of Lausanne in Switzerland. Going through the ACA-401 course file, I remember how demanding it is from a linguistic, grammatical and syntactical point of view to write an academic essay, this time in English. I also remember how important it is to be accompanied throughout the writing process. I find that the ACA-401 course file reassures the student that I am on his path to take and on its different stages. This is all the more important since not being an English speaker, I do not master the codes and subtleties of English writing when it comes to using it in the context of an academic essay.

In this response paper, I want to discuss how one constructs an essay, from the analysis of the question to the structure of its writing. I also present the importance to ensure the consistency of the text in its syntax, in the choice of the linguistic variant and through the adoption of a coherent style. I end by recalling the importance of avoiding plagiarism.

2) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY: FROM RESEARCHING THE TOPIC TO STRUCTURING THE RESPONSE

Whatever the literary work, its writing always requires the application of a method. Few are the writers who, like Victor Hugo or Honoré de Balzac, have the innate ability to write captivating 300-page novels at the corner of a table. The academic essay is no exception to this rule, especially since the formal requirements meet a well-established process in the scientific framework (EUCLID 2021, 7).

This process begins with the in-depth study of the subject posed by the question to be answered. This study, augmented with notes, makes it possible to clearly define the contours of the problem both with a critical and creative mindset. It also makes it possible to gather the sources from which the student can draw evidence supporting his statements, compare points of view or deepen his analysis (EUCLID 2021, 8-9) of the question.

It is on the basis of this research that the next step can be initiated: establishing a writing plan. The importance of this step lies in the fact that it allows the student to organize his ideas according to the possible answer identified during the research step (EUCLID 2021, 9-10). The writing plan (or structure of the academic essay) is made of four parts: an introduction, a body, a conclusion and a reference list (EUCLID 2021, 10-11).

In the introduction, the student exposes the topic, identifies the various approaches and proposes a response. In the body of the essay, the student develops the proposed answer by adding evidence and references to demonstrate its validity. The conclusion is then used by the student to summarize the points of discussion by rephrasing them and to propose, based on the elaborated response, avenues for future potential developments.

3) CHOOSING A VARIANT: AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

Any language has variants. Living in Switzerland, I speak French as twenty two percent of the Swiss population (Office fédéral de la statistique, 2019). However, Swiss French differs from the French of France both in its vocabulary and in its style. It is the same for the language of Shakespeare whose developments and variations are essentially linked to various historical developments.

In the last mid-century, American English became the predominant language used internationally, reflecting the hegemony of the United States of America after World War II. Originally the reference in the English language, British English became another variant like American English of what is called World English (EUCLID 2021, 25).

EUCLID (2021, 25) proposes that the student choose between American English and British English as the reference variant to be used all along. Choosing one variant and

sticking to it is critical for the consistency of the writing. It is also for its understanding, as the meaning of a word, of a sentence, of an idea can be affected depending on the variant chosen.

The variance between American English and British English is reflected through many language categories (EUCLID 2021, 25-32): pronunciation and spelling, meaning of words spelled identically, syntax and grammar, punctuation, the use of periods, commas and quotation marks for instance. Culture and political contexts may also explain some of the differences between American English and British English.

4) PLAGIARISM

Many sources (books, articles, newspapers, magazines and so on) are available online. It has therefore become easier for a student to copy and paste in his text entire paragraphs, sentences of other authors or even to draw inspiration from the ideas of others.

Such a practice is called plagiarism when the student does not explicitly identify paragraphs, sentences or ideas borrowed from other authors and reference them as their sources (EUCLID 2021, 34). Beyond the unethical nature of this practice, plagiarism also calls into question the scientific nature of the academic essay and its originality.

EUCLID (2021, 34-38) lists all the methods that allows the student to avoid plagiarism. It includes the proper use of quotations, including their frequency and length in the text. EUCLID (2021, 36) recommends also to limit the use of quotations by expressing an idea through our own words. This is called paraphrasing. It responds to the same rule of referencing the author.

5) STYLE GUIDES

Ensuring consistency in an academic essay is critical. As discussed above (point n° 3), choosing a language variant is important. However, this is not the only element that must be enforced for that matter. Choosing a style is also essential to ensure the consistency throughout the essay.

Style guides provide the student with the necessary guidance to ensure that sentence length, manuscript format, use of abbreviations, symbols, or word choice are consistent throughout the process of writing (EUCLID 2021, 41-42).

The benefit of sticking to one style is also, beyond consistency, to avoid misreading and misunderstanding that could impact the understanding of an essay and its impact. Euclide is suggesting a diversity of guide styles that the student can adopt: the Economist style guide, the BBC News style guide and so one. Euclide (2021, 41) recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian).

6) HOW AND WHEN TO USE LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

The use of Latin abbreviations is common in academic French. This certainly comes from the proximity of the language of Molière to that of Cicero. In writing in American English, the use of Latin abbreviations is limited to notes, bibliographical references and in more informal settings (EUCLID 2021, 59). For academic, technical, or business essays, the English equivalent of the Latin abbreviation is preferred.

Euclid (2021, 59-64) provides the student with two tables listing a series of commonly used Latin abbreviations and their equivalents in English. It is indicated to refer to these tables when writing the academic essay.

7) CONCLUSION

Writing an academic essay is not a process that is left unguided and unframed. There are rules of style, structure or language to which it is necessary to comply because they ensure the scientific character of the writing, its coherence and its ease of reading. These rules are described in various documents, works which are available to the student so that he becomes familiar with them. Euclid (2021) also gives a good summary.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Duke University. N.d. Paragraphing: The MEAL Plan. Accessed February 09, 2022. <https://twp.duke.edu/sites/twp.duke.edu/files/file-attachments/meal-plan.original.pdf>.

Secrist, Matt, n.d. What is a Style Guide? Main Elements of a Great Style Guide. Accessed November 11, 2022 [What Is A Style Guide? Main Elements of a Great Guide - BKA Content](#)

Purdue University, n.d. "Style Guide Overview." Accessed November 01, 2022. [Style Guide Overview - Purdue OWL® - Purdue University](#)

Satar, Dina, n.d. What is a Writing Style Guide, and Which One Should You Use? Accessed November 03, 2022 [What Is a Writing Style Guide, and Which One Should You Use? \(thewritelife.com\)](#)

P.Org, n.d. What is Plagiarism? Accessed November 10, 2022 [What is Plagiarism? - Plagiarism.org](#)

Lee, Chelsea, n.d. It's All Latin to Me: Latin Abbreviations in Scholarly Writing. Accessed November 09, 2022 [APA Style 6th Edition Blog: It's All Latin to Me: Latin Abbreviations in Scholarly Writing](#)

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.